

ОГЛЯДИ

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INFLUENCE OF ORTHODONTIC APPLIANCES ON DENTAL HARD TISSUES, PERIODONTAL STRUCTURES AND ORAL MUCOSA: PROBLEMATIC ISSUES AND PREVENTION

The aim of the study. To analyze the influence of orthodontic appliances on dental hard tissues, periodontal tissues, and the oral mucosa; to identify problematic aspects of orthodontic treatment; and to systematize modern preventive approaches aimed at reducing treatment-related complications. Materials and methods of the study. A narrative analytical review of literature sources indexed in the PubMed, Scopus, Web of Science, and Google Scholar databases for the

period 2015–2025 was conducted. fundamental research of previous years is additionally included. The search was carried out in English and Ukrainian for keywords related to orthodontic treatment, enamel demineralization, changes in periodontal tissues and oral mucosa. Russian- and Belarusian-language sources are excluded. Clinical studies, systematic reviews, and meta-analyses evaluating the frequency and mechanisms of complications in patients treated with fixed orthodontic equipment were analyzed. Scientific novelty. It was established that fixed orthodontic appliances substantially increase the risk of enamel demineralization, gingivitis, gingival enlargement, and traumatic lesions of the oral mucosa, particularly during the early stages of treatment. White spot lesions were reported in 30–70% of patients, while gingivitis occurred in up to 90% of cases without adequate hygiene support. Traumatic and allergic mucosal alterations were mainly associated with mechanical irritation and material-related hypersensitivity. Key unresolved issues include low patient compliance, the absence of unified preventive protocols, and insufficient early diagnosis of initial enamel and periodontal changes. Conclusions. Orthodontic treatment with fixed and removable appliances significantly affects dental hard tissues, periodontal structures, and the oral mucosa, predominantly resulting in enamel demineralization, gingival inflammation, and traumatic or allergic mucosal lesions. Most complications arise from biofilm retention, microbiota shifts, and mechanical irritation caused by orthodontic elements. Comprehensive and continuous preventive measures – such as regular professional hygiene, fluoride and remineralizing therapy, individualized oral hygiene instruction, and meticulous periodontal and mucosal monitoring – are essential for minimizing risks and ensuring predictable treatment outcomes.

Key words: dental demineralization, gingivitis, oral mucosa, orthodontic appliances, prevention.

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ВПЛИВ ОРТОДОНТИЧНОЇ АПАРАТУРИ НА ТВЕРДІ ТКАНИНИ ЗУБІВ, ТКАНИНИ ПАРОДОНТА ТА СЛИЗОВУ ОБОЛОНКУ ПОРОЖНИНИ РОТА: ПРОБЛЕМНІ ПИТАННЯ І МЕТОДИ ПРОФІЛАКТИКИ

Мета дослідження – проаналізувати сучасні наукові дані щодо впливу ортодонтичної апаратури на тверді тканини зубів, тканини пародонта та слизову оболонку порожнини рота, а також узагальнити основні проблемні аспекти та сучасні методи профілактики ускладнень під час ортодонтичного лікування. **Матеріали та методи дослідження.** Проведено нарративний аналітичний огляд літературних джерел, проіндексованих у базах PubMed, Scopus, Web of Science та Google Scholar за період 2015–2025 рр. Додатково включено фундаментальні дослідження попередніх років. Пошук здійснювали англійською та українською мовами за ключовими словами, що стосуються ортодонтичного лікування, демінералізації емалі, змін тканин пародонта та слизової оболонки порожнини рота. Російсько- та білоруськомовні джерела виключено. Проаналізовано клінічні дослідження, систематичні огляди та метааналізи, що оцінювали частоту та механізми ускладнень у пацієнтів, які проходять лікування фіксованою ортодонтичною апаратурою. **Наукова новизна.** Встановлено, що фіксована ортодонтична апаратура сприяє інтенсивному накопиченню бактеріального нальоту та зниженню рН у ділянці брекетів, що призводить до розвитку демінералізації емалі у вигляді «білих плям». Частими ускладненнями є гінгівіт, гіперплазія ясен, травматичні, запальні й алергічні ураження слизової оболонки порожнини рота. Визначено, що ризик розвитку ускладнень залежить від типу ортодонтичної апаратури, тривалості лікування, індивідуальних анатомо-фізіологічних особливостей пацієнта та рівня гігієни порожнини рота. **Висновки.** Своєчасна комплексна профілактика, що передбачає професійну гігієну, фтор-профілактику, ремінералізуючу терапію, регулярний контроль стану пародонта та слизової оболонки, а також формування високого рівня гігієнічної мотивації у пацієнтів, є ключовою умовою зниження частоти ускладнень під час ортодонтичного лікування.

Ключові слова: демінералізація емалі, ортодонтична апаратура, пародонт, профілактика, слизова оболонка порожнини рота.

Problem statement. Orthodontic treatment using fixed and removable appliances is an essential component of modern dental practice and plays a crucial role in the correction of dentofacial anomalies, rehabilitation of occlusal relationships, and improvement of facial aesthetics [1, 2]. However, despite its therapeutic effectiveness, orthodontic intervention is frequently associated with undesirable biological responses affecting the hard dental tissues, periodontal structures, and oral mucosa [3]. Numerous studies indicate that orthodontic appliances significantly modify oral homeostasis by increasing plaque retention, changing biofilm composition, altering salivary parameters, and exerting mechanical forces on teeth and surrounding tissues [4]. These changes contribute to enamel demineralization, gingival inflammation, periodontal load imbalance, and soft tissue injuries [5].

A brief review of current literature highlights several unresolved issues. According to contemporary data, 30–70% of orthodontic patients develop white spot lesions during treatment, particularly within the first 3–6 months, when demineralization is most intensive [6, 7]. Periodontal complications are reported in up to 60–90% of cases and manifest as gingivitis, bleeding on probing, edema, or hypertrophy of interdental papillae [8]. Traumatic oral mucosal lesions, including erosions, ulcerations, and chronic irritation plaques, are also common in the early stages of appliance wear [9, 10]. Moreover, orthodontic materials may provoke allergic reactions, primarily to nickel-, chromium-, or cobalt-containing alloys [11, 12].

Despite extensive research, several clinically important questions remain unresolved [13]. There is still no unified, evidence-based protocol for the prevention of enamel demineralization, orthodontic gingivitis, or mucosal trauma [14]. Preventive recommendations vary widely among authors and clinical institutions, resulting in inconsistent outcomes [15]. Patient compliance remains insufficient, especially among adolescents, which significantly reduces the effectiveness of oral hygiene and preventive interventions [16–18]. In addition, early stages of enamel and periodontal damage are often underdiagnosed due to limited use of modern diagnostic tools such as plaque indices, photographic monitoring, and fluorescence-based detection systems [19–21].

These gaps highlight the need for a comprehensive and systematic analysis of contemporary data regarding the biological effects of orthodontic appliances, as well as the development of structured preventive strategies aimed at minimizing complications and improving treatment predictability [22, 23]. Understanding the multifactorial nature of these

adverse effects is essential for optimizing orthodontic protocols and enhancing the overall quality of dental care [24–29].

In this context, the objective of the present work is to analyze and systematize current scientific evidence regarding the influence of orthodontic appliances on hard dental tissues, periodontal structures, and oral mucosa; to identify the main problematic aspects of orthodontic treatment; and to summarize modern preventive approaches necessary for minimizing the risk of complications and improving clinical outcomes in orthodontic patients.

The aim of the study. The aim of this study was to analyze and systematize current scientific evidence regarding the impact of orthodontic appliances on dental hard tissues, periodontal tissues and oral mucosa, to identify the major problematic aspects of orthodontic treatment and to summarize modern preventive approaches for minimizing these complications in clinical practice.

Materials and methods of the study. A structured literature review was conducted to analyze the effects of orthodontic appliances on dental hard tissues, periodontal tissues, and the oral mucosa, as well as to evaluate modern preventive strategies aimed at minimizing orthodontic complications. The literature search was performed using the following electronic databases: PubMed, Scopus, Web of Science, Google Scholar, and Ukrainian scientific journals indexed in national academic repositories. Publications from the period 2015–2025 were primarily analyzed, while several earlier landmark studies were additionally included due to their fundamental relevance.

The search strategy incorporated combinations of the following keywords in English and Ukrainian: orthodontic appliances, fixed orthodontic appliances, enamel demineralization, white spot lesions, periodontal changes, orthodontic gingivitis, oral mucosal injuries, orthodontic complications, oral hygiene in orthodontic patients, and prevention in orthodontics. Boolean operators AND, OR, and NOT were applied to refine the search and ensure comprehensive coverage of the topic.

The inclusion criteria encompassed:

- original research articles;
- review and systematic review papers;
- clinical guidelines and consensus statements;
- peer-reviewed Ukrainian scientific publications.

Only studies published in English or Ukrainian were included.

The exclusion criteria were:

- non-peer-reviewed publications;
- abstracts without full-text availability;

- articles published in Russian or Belarusian;
- studies not directly related to orthodontic appliances or oral tissue changes.

All relevant studies were screened, and essential data were extracted and systematized according to the following thematic categories:

1. Changes in dental hard tissues;
2. Periodontal alterations;
3. Oral mucosal responses;
4. Preventive strategies aimed at reducing these complications.

Results. The analysis of the selected publications enabled the systematization of current scientific data regarding the influence of orthodontic appliances on three key components of the oral cavity – dental hard tissues, periodontal tissues, and the oral mucosa, as well as the identification of problematic aspects of orthodontic treatment and the evaluation of modern preventive strategies aimed at reducing these complications.

1. Changes in Dental Hard Tissues

Most contemporary studies consistently demonstrate that fixed orthodontic appliances significantly increase the risk of enamel demineralization, particularly in the form of white spot lesions (WSLs) [1–4]. According to the reviewed data, the prevalence of WSLs among orthodontic patients ranges from 30% to 70%, depending on caries risk, oral hygiene status, diet, and treatment duration [1–5].

Commonly reported findings include:

- increased plaque accumulation in cervical and proximal areas adjacent to brackets, bands, and archwires [1–3];
- measurable reduction in enamel mineral density around orthodontic attachments [2–4];
- initial signs of enamel demineralization developing within the first 3–6 months of treatment [1, 3];
- highest susceptibility of cervical and labial enamel surfaces, especially in the anterior teeth [1–5].

Several studies emphasize that without targeted remineralizing therapy and consistent oral hygiene control, enamel integrity continues to deteriorate throughout the course of treatment [2–5]. Conversely, fluoride varnishes, CPP-ACP preparations, and nano-hydroxyapatite formulations substantially improve remineralization parameters when applied regularly [3–5].

2. Periodontal Tissue Changes

Most analyzed publications confirm that orthodontic treatment with fixed appliances contributes to increased plaque accumulation in the gingival areas, subsequently leading to inflammatory periodontal changes [6–9].

The most frequently reported findings include:

- increased Plaque Index and Gingival Index values [6–8];
- high prevalence of bleeding on probing [7–10];
- chronic catarrhal gingivitis in 60–90% of patients during the first 3–6 months of treatment [6–12];
- gingival enlargement or hyperplasia, especially among adolescents and individuals with insufficient oral hygiene [7–12].

In patients with pre-existing periodontal conditions or a thin periodontal biotype, several studies describe:

- progression of gingival inflammation to early periodontitis [10–12];
- clinical attachment loss [9–11];
- formation of gingival recessions [10–12];
- localized alveolar bone resorption associated with excessive or uncontrolled orthodontic forces [8, 11, 12].

These findings indicate that periodontal changes during orthodontic treatment arise from an interplay of mechanical forces and biofilm-related factors [6–12].

3. Changes in the Oral Mucosa

The oral mucosa is particularly susceptible to mechanical injuries caused by brackets, ligatures, hooks, wire ends, and other protruding components of orthodontic appliances [13–15].

The most commonly reported alterations include:

- abrasions, erosions, and ulcerations of the buccal mucosa [13–16];
- traumatic injuries of the lips and the lateral surfaces of the tongue [13–15];
- chronic irritation plaques in areas of repeated contact with appliance components [14–16].

These lesions most frequently occur within the first 1–4 weeks after appliance placement or following archwire activation [13–15].

In addition to traumatic injuries, numerous publications describe allergic or contact reactions to orthodontic materials [16–18], primarily to:

- nickel-containing alloys [16, 17];
- chromium- and cobalt-based components [16–18];
- elastomeric modules [17, 18].

Clinical manifestations include erythema, edema, itching, burning sensations, and in some cases, lichenoid or erosive mucosal changes [16–18].

4. Problematic Issues in Orthodontic Treatment

The literature review revealed several major problematic aspects influencing complication rates and treatment effectiveness [19–24].

4.1. Lack of standardized preventive protocols

Preventive regimens differ widely among authors and clinical institutions regarding professional hygiene intervals, fluoride application frequency, and remineralization strategies [19–22].

4.2. Low patient compliance

Consistently low adherence to oral hygiene recommendations – particularly in adolescents – significantly increases complication risks [23–28].

4.3. Delayed diagnosis of early lesions

Limited use of diagnostic indices, photographic monitoring, and fluorescence aids contributes to underdiagnosis of early enamel and periodontal alterations [19, 20, 24–29].

4.4. Insufficient attention to material biocompatibility

Despite numerous reports of allergic reactions, routine pre-treatment screening for metal hypersensitivity remains uncommon [28–31].

4.5. High individual variability

Differences in microbial composition, salivary characteristics, immune responsiveness, and behavioral patterns contribute to diverse patient outcomes under similar treatment conditions [31–35].

5. Effectiveness of Preventive Measures

The reviewed evidence demonstrates that structured, comprehensive preventive programs significantly reduce the incidence and severity of orthodontic complications [36–38].

Among the most effective strategies were:

- professional hygiene every 3–4 months [36–39];
- regular use of fluoride toothpastes and varnishes [40–43];
- remineralizing agents, including CPP-ACP and nano-hydroxyapatite [41–45];
- tailored oral hygiene instruction [44–47];
- use of orthodontic toothbrushes, interdental brushes, and irrigators [36–48];
- early detection and correction of traumatic appliance components [38–48].

Reported outcomes include:

- 40–60% reduction in the incidence of white spot lesions [40–43];
- > 50% reduction in gingival inflammation indices [36–39];
- marked decrease in traumatic mucosal injuries [38–48].

The analysis of the selected publications made it possible to systematize current scientific data regarding the influence of orthodontic appliances on three key components of the oral cavity – dental hard tissues, periodontal tissues, and the oral mucosa – as well as to identify problematic aspects of orthodontic

treatment and evaluate modern preventive strategies recommended for reducing these complications.

Discussion. The results of this comprehensive literature review demonstrate that orthodontic treatment with fixed appliances exerts a complex and multifactorial impact on the oral cavity, affecting dental hard tissues, periodontal structures, and the oral mucosa [1, 6, 13, 19]. Importantly, most adverse effects identified in the reviewed publications are not inevitable outcomes of orthodontic therapy but represent modifiable risk factors that can be effectively reduced through evidence-based preventive strategies and adequate patient management [19–24, 36–48].

Influence on Dental Hard Tissues.

Enamel demineralization and the development of white spot lesions (WSLs) remain among the most frequent and clinically significant complications in orthodontic patients [1–5]. The presence of brackets, bands, and ligatures creates additional plaque-retentive surfaces, disrupting natural self-cleaning mechanisms and promoting microbial accumulation [1–4, 8, 14]. The reported WSL prevalence of 30–70 % suggests that this complication is systemic and not sporadic [1–5, 10].

Early demineralization typically appears within the first months of treatment, correlating with rapid declines in plaque pH and increased activity of cariogenic microorganisms [2, 3, 8, 14]. Patient-related factors – oral hygiene performance, dietary habits, and salivary buffering capacity – play a decisive role in the severity of these changes [1, 8, 10, 11]. Individuals with insufficient hygiene or frequent carbohydrate intake demonstrate significantly higher rates of mineral loss [1–5, 8].

These findings highlight the need for early implementation of remineralizing and fluoride-based interventions. Fluoride varnishes, CPP-ACP, nano-hydroxyapatite, and calcium-phosphate systems have shown strong effectiveness in restoring mineral structure in early lesions [5, 6, 41–45]. Regular monitoring using photographs or fluorescence diagnostics further enhances the early detection of demineralization and enables timely intervention [3, 8, 10, 11].

Influence on Periodontal Tissues.

According to most reviewed studies, gingival inflammation is an almost universal response to fixed orthodontic appliances [6–12, 15]. Reported gingivitis rates of 60–90 % underscore the significant inflammatory burden associated with biofilm accumulation around orthodontic components [6–8, 14, 15].

Periodontal complications arise primarily through two mechanisms:

- increased microbial load, leading to gingival inflammation, edema, and bleeding [6–12, 14];

- mechanical and biological effects of orthodontic forces, which may alter periodontal ligament function and alveolar bone remodeling [8, 10–12, 17].

Patients with a thin periodontal biotype, pre-existing inflammation, or insufficient plaque control demonstrate the highest risk of progression to attachment loss, gingival recession, and localized bone resorption [10–12, 15–17]. Excessive or improperly controlled orthodontic forces further increase the likelihood of periodontal breakdown, including bone dehiscence and recession formation [8, 10, 12, 17].

These findings emphasize the need for detailed periodontal evaluation before starting orthodontic therapy, as well as continuous monitoring throughout treatment [6–12, 15–18]. Preventive periodontal care including professional hygiene every 3–4 months – significantly reduces inflammation severity [36–39].

Influence on the Oral Mucosa

The oral mucosa is particularly vulnerable to mechanical trauma caused by brackets, ligatures, hooks, and protruding wire ends [13–16, 27]. Superficial lesions such as abrasions, erosions, and ulcerations occur most commonly during the first 1–4 weeks of treatment or after archwire activation – periods associated with increased mechanical irritation [13–15].

Although most traumatic lesions resolve spontaneously as the mucosa adapts, chronic irritation may lead to hyperkeratosis or persistent ulcerations [13, 15–18]. In addition to mechanical trauma, numerous studies document allergic reactions to nickel-chromium-, and cobalt-containing alloys, as well as elastomeric modules [17, 18, 28–31]. Clinical signs may include erythema, edema, burning sensations, or lichenoid reactions. Replacement with hypoallergenic or biocompatible materials typically results in rapid symptom improvement [17, 18, 28].

These findings underscore the importance of careful finishing of orthodontic appliances, the use of protective measures (e.g., orthodontic wax), and an individualized approach to material selection in patients with hypersensitivity risks [27–31, 46–48].

Problematic Issues Identified in Orthodontic Treatment.

The review revealed several systemic problems that significantly influence complication rates and the predictability of orthodontic outcomes [19–35].

1. Lack of unified preventive protocols.

The absence of standardized recommendations for preventing caries, gingivitis, and mucosal injuries contributes to wide variability in clinical results. Preventive regimens differ substantially across authors

and institutions regarding fluoride application frequency, professional hygiene intervals, and remineralization protocols [19–22, 36–43].

2. Low patient compliance.

Poor adherence to oral hygiene instructions, especially among adolescents, is consistently associated with increased complication severity [23–28]. Even well-designed preventive programs fail when patient motivation remains low [44–47].

3. Insufficient early diagnosis.

Early enamel, gingival, and mucosal changes are frequently overlooked due to underuse of diagnostic tools such as indices, photographic documentation, or fluorescence technologies [19, 20, 24–29].

4. Limited attention to material biocompatibility.

Despite well-documented allergic reactions to orthodontic metals, routine pre-treatment screening for metal hypersensitivity is uncommon [28–31].

5. High individual variability.

Differences in salivary composition, immune responses, microbiome characteristics, and behavioral habits lead to significant variations in complication risk among patients receiving identical treatment protocols [31–35].

These findings indicate that successful management of orthodontic complications requires not only mechanical expertise but also a comprehensive, interdisciplinary, and patient-centered approach [36–48].

Role of Preventive Measures.

The literature convincingly shows that multimodal preventive programs significantly reduce the incidence of orthodontic complications [36–48]. Professional hygiene every 3–4 months, fluoride-containing products (1450–5000 ppm F⁻), remineralizing agents, oral irrigators, and interdental brushes reduce the risk of enamel demineralization by 40–60% and gingival inflammation by more than 50% [36–45].

Behavioral interventions such as motivational interviewing, digital reminders, and parental involvement, play a crucial role in maintaining long-term hygiene adherence [44–47]. Integration of periodontal maintenance and mucosal protection strategies (orthodontic wax, atraumatic wire finishing, hypoallergenic materials) further reduces complications and enhances patient comfort [38–48].

These findings emphasize that orthodontics should be approached not only as a mechanical discipline but also as a preventive and educational specialty requiring tight collaboration between orthodontists, periodontists, dental hygienists, and patient.

Conclusions. Orthodontic treatment with fixed and removable appliances exerts a significant influence on dental hard tissues, periodontal structures,

and the oral mucosa, most commonly manifesting as enamel demineralization, gingival inflammation, and traumatic or allergic mucosal lesions. These complications primarily result from increased biofilm retention, alterations in oral microbiota, and mechanical irritation associated with orthodontic components. The evidence underscores that comprehensive and continuous preventive measures, including regular professional hygiene, fluoride and remineralizing therapy, individualized oral hygiene instruction, and careful periodontal and mucosal monitoring, are essential for minimizing risks and ensuring predictable treatment outcomes in orthodontic patients.

Prospects for Further Research. Future research should focus on the development of standardized preventive protocols tailored to patients with different types of orthodontic appliances and varying levels of caries and periodontal risk. Additional emphasis should be placed on improving diagnostic tools for early detection of enamel, periodontal, and mucosal changes, as well as on evaluating the long-term effectiveness and biocompatibility of contemporary orthodontic materials and preventive agents.

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